

Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol by Chromium (VI) in 90 Percent Acetone Solution

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The oxidation of allyl alcohol by chromium (VI) in 90 percent acetone resembles the oxidation of 2-propanol by chromium (VI) in several respects and is understood to follow a similar mechanism.

THE oxidation of allyl alcohol (AA) by chromium(VI) in acetone solution results in quantitative yields of the aldehyde¹ and involves no breakage of the double bond². No kinetic study of the reaction is available in the literature and we give here the results of our study in 90 percent acetone solution.

Experimental

AA (Kochlight) was distilled from potassium carbonate³ and had a b.p. of 94° (n_D^{25} 1.412). Acetone was refluxed for several hours over potassium permanganate⁴ and then distilled at 56°. Perchloric acid (E. Merck) and potassium dichromate (AR) were used as such. *p*-Nitroaniline (BDH) was recrystallised (m.p. 146°). Other chemicals were reagent grade.

Kinetic runs in 90 percent acetone solution were followed by frequently withdrawing reaction samples which were then analysed by back titration of excess standard ferrous solution with standard potassium dichromate solution using barium diphenylamine sulpho-nate as indicator. Most runs were followed to about 60 percent reaction.

Product analysis showed acrolein as the main product of oxidation. Acidity function, H_0 , of different solutions was determined using *p*-nitroaniline. The possibility of radical intervention during the oxidation of AA in 90 percent acetone was examined by addition of acrylamide as in the case of 2-propanol oxidation in aqueous acetic acid⁵. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at 25°, its volume reduced by distilling off excess acetone and methanol was added when a polymer precipitated. Similar experiments in the absence of the alcohol or in the absence of acrylamide did not lead to polymer formation.

Discussion

Variation of the concentrations each of the substrate (AA), oxidant and acid while keeping the others fixed showed that the reaction was first order each in substrate, oxidant and acid (Tables 1-3). The activation energy and entropy of activation were respectively 11.4 kcal mole⁻¹ and -26 e.u. which may be compared with

the data for the 2-propanol oxidation in 50 percent acetic acid of 13.6 kcal mole⁻¹ and -33 e.u. The lower activation energy and less negative entropy of activation of AA oxidation are indicative of the stabilisation of the activated complex by the presence of the double bond in the substrate. The rate of oxidation increases with increasing acetone content in

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF CONCENTRATION OF CHROMIUM (VI) ON THE FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT.

Chromium (VI) (M) × 10 ³	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.834	5.68
1.67	5.60
2.33	5.35
3.33	5.48

[Allyl alc.] = 0.512 M ; [HClO₄] = 0.0918 M
Medium, 90 percent acetone at 0°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF ACIDITY ON RATE CONSTANT.

Concentration of acid (HClO ₄) M × 10 ³	Acidity function H ₀	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	log k ₁ = log k ₁ + H ₀
4.57	2.10	3.02	-1.42
9.10	1.82	5.60	-1.43
18.2	1.49	15.01	-1.33
27.4	0.980	37.1	-1.45
36.5	-	53.7	-

[Cr(VI)] = 0.00167 M ; [allyl alc.] = 0.512 M

* H₀ could not be determined
Medium, 90 percent acetone at 0°.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CHANGE OF CONCENTRATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL ON RATE CONSTANT

Concentration of allyl alc. (M) × 10 ³	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ⁸ litre mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$\frac{k_1 \times 10^5}{[\text{allyl alc.}]}$
7.32	9.49		1.30
13.2	14.4		1.10
26.3	31.0		1.17
51.2	56.0		1.09

[Cr(VI)] = 0.00167 M ; [HClO₄] = 0.0918 M

90 percent acetone medium at 0°.

the solvent. Such rate increases in less polar solvents have been ascribed to the facility of formation of chromate esters⁶. In all these respects the reaction resembles the oxidation of 2-propanol⁷.

The rate of oxidation of AA decreases in the presence of added chloride ions at constant ionic strength. Such a rate lowering in presence of chloride ions is also observed in the case of 2-propanol oxidation. The active oxidant in chromic acid oxidations is HCrO₄⁻ and in presence of chloride ions this species is replaced by the less active HCrO₃Cl⁻ which is responsible for the rate lowering⁸. Not only chloride but also other anions affect the rate of oxidation in their own distinctive fashion presumably due to the formation of the species, HCrO₃A⁻⁹. In this respect we have found a close parallelism between the oxidation of AA and the oxidation of 2-propanol. In view of such results, we conclude that the mechanisms in the two cases are similar.

Recently a free radical mechanism has been found by Rahman and Rocek for the oxidation of 2-propanol by chromium(VI) in aqueous acetic acid⁵. The use of free radical scavengers like acrylamide was found by them to give rise to polymer formation. Analogous scavenging experiments by us in the case of the oxidation of AA in 90 percent acetone also showed polymer formation. We have compared the two cases and find similar results. In the absence of the alcohol or in the absence of the scavenger, acrylamide, no polymer formation occurs. This evidence along with the results stated above leads to a free radical mechanism of aldehyde formation :

A chromate ester is formed in a termolecular equilibrium step followed by a rate determining decomposition of ester. Then followed a series of rapid steps which involve intermediate oxidation states of chromium, Cr(IV) and Cr(V)⁵.

The effect of addition of pyrazole on the AA oxidation in 90 percent acetone provided interesting results. Addition of 0.02M and 0.04M pyrazole caused rate increases from 5.58 × 10⁻⁴ sec⁻¹ to 7.03 × 10⁻⁴ sec⁻¹ and 7.40 × 10⁻⁴ sec⁻¹ respectively. The complex of pyrazole with chromium(VI) is an excellent oxidising agent in methylene chloride¹⁰ and presumably the co-ordination of pyrazole to chromium(VI) aids the formation of the activated complex thus leading to higher rates of oxidation in these solutions.

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